

An evaluation of compression properties of stir-casted magnesium alloy AZ91 through experimental and numerical methods

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Abstract

Present study describes the basic compression properties of magnesium alloy AZ91. Novel and economical stir casting technique is used to prepare the samples under protected atmosphere. In addition finite element analysis (FEA) also adopted to evaluate the compression properties. The stir-casted samples are analysed in as-cast condition at room temperature. The XRD results indicated the presence of α -Mg phase and the secondary Mg₁₇Al₁₂ intermetallic phases in the microstructure study. The surface morphology study was performed through SEM analysis. The outcome of uniaxial compression test revealed that produced AZ91 alloy exhibited ultimate compressive strength as 243 MPa and compressive yield strength as 120 MPa and 10% ductility. The numerical study was carried out for 5 mm and 10 mm deflection under compressive load, and its outcome stated that more stress intensity and broader plastic deformation also obtained for 10 mm compression sample.

Keywords: magnesium, heat treatment, stir casting, ultimate compressive strength, finite element analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The light weight structural material such as magnesium based alloys and composites are gaining more attention in present days due to increasing needs [1-4]. Kandemir et al., 2021 [5] analysed the microstructure at high-temperature mechanical performance, and creep characteristics of the AZ91 alloy and its composites, which contained varying amounts (2.5 and 5 wt.%) and lengths (100 and 500 μm) of recycled carbon fibers, within a temperature range of 25–200 °C. The outcome of this study demonstrated that the high shear dispersion technique resulted in finer grains and a more uniform fiber distribution within the cast composites. In addition that compressive creep testing indicated that the composites reinforced with recycled carbon fibers exhibited similar or higher minimum creep rates compared to the unreinforced AZ91 alloy. The compression behavior analysed through finite element method by Hongshuai Lei et al. 2019 [6] and presents and uniaxial compression tests are conducted to assess how the presence of defects and the number of layers affect the mechanical behavior and energy absorption performance of the panels for SLM-fabricated multi-layer lattice structures. Maurice et al. 2005 [7] studied aluminium alloy compression behavior at elevated temperature. And demonstrated that high-temperature slip systems, hot deformation textures, and microstructures, and the behavior of constituent particles are showed to illustrate the benefits of the elevated temperature channel-die compression (CDC) technique. Paramsothy et al. 2009 [8] examined both tensile and compression behavior on AZ31 magnesium alloy reinforced with alumina (Al_2O_3) particle and observed nanoparticle Al_2O_3 reinforcement on the enhancement of both tensile and compressive properties of AZ31. Park et al. 2014 [9] explained twinning characteristics of randomly textured magnesium alloy. The tension experiment states that, the continuous twinning effect after yielding and nucleation-dominant twinning behavior creates an unclear yield point and increased strain hardening. But, in compression test, resulted simultaneous twinning in multiple grains and superior twinning behavior produces a relatively different yield point and a low strain hardening rate. Similar twinning effect studied by Sun et al. 2019 [10]. Rokni et al. 2011 [11] states that the constitutive equations should accurately capture the flow characteristics of the materials. Steglich et al. 2014 [12] analysed the compression behavior of rolled

magnesium alloy AZ31 and ZE10 and states that different hardening rate possessed significant effect in the compression behavior. Tahreen et al. 2014 [13] analysed the effect of addition of aluminium alloy and strain rate on compression properties of magnesium alloy was studied and concluded that strength coefficient enhanced with increasing aluminum content. Sandar Tun et al. 2021 [14] indicated the change in microstructure, significantly improved compressive strength were obtained in extruded magnesium alloy as compared to cast magnesium alloy due to intermetallics morphology as discontinuous pattern. Wang et al. 2001 [15] analysed non-linear finite element analysis (FEA) model reinforced concrete structure and concluded that FEA results good agreement with experiment results. Watanabe and Fukusumi 2014 [16] investigated uniaxial tension and compression experiment of the extruded magnesium alloys along the longitudinal direction, and outcome states incoherence was demonstrated using the hypothesis that sliding of grain-boundary under tension is easier than under compression.

From the previous literatures available indicates the study on compression behavior is one of the essential analysis to understand about microstructure and compression behavior. In addition very few literatures only available for stir casted magnesium alloy compression behavior through experimental and numerical methods. Hence present work aimed to understand the compression properties of stir-casted magnesium alloy AZ91.

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Production of magnesium-based alloy AZ91

Stir casting is one of the conventional and novel and economical methods to prepare magnesium-based materials. In this method pure Mg, pure Al and zinc raw materials are added and melted as per the alloy composition (Al 9 wt.%, Zn 1 wt.% 0.5 Mn wt.% balance Mg) [3]. All the raw materials are melted into molten form by heating the materials to above its melting point of all matrix materials. Then add the matrix material by descending order according to its melting point temperatures in order to get all the metal elements in the casting metal. In order to obtain uniform distribution of all materials in all direction the mechanical stirrer is allowed to rotate with 500 rpm for sufficient duration. Then the molten alloy material is poured in to preheated mold and solidified into room temperature. Fig. 1 indicates the pouring the molten metal into preheated die. Fig. 2 indicates the stir casted sample i.e magnesium alloy AZ91.

Fig. 01 Preparation of cast metal

Fig. 02 Produced stir-casted sample

2.2 Ageing heat treatment

The stir-casted samples of AZ91 were subjected to ageing heat treatment process. According to ASTM B661-06 standard, T6- solution heat treatment followed by artificial ageing were selected for this present work. Solution heat treatment (SHT) was performed at 350°C for 4 hours followed by water quenching method. Then natural ageing carried out at 100 °C for one day (24 hours).

2.3 Sample Preparation through wire cut EDM process

Wire cut Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) is one of the widely employed method for preparing samples as per ASTM standard with intricate geometries and high dimensional accuracy. In this present work stircasted samples are subjected to wirecut EDM process. The cylindrical samples having diameter $13 \text{ mm} \times 25 \text{ mm}$ (ASTM E-09) were prepared for compression test. And 5 mm thickness samples prepared for microstructural study.

2.4 Uniaxial compression test

ASTM E09 standard was followed to measure the compression properties. This compression test was carried out in the room temperature. Compressive properties of the material such as compressive yield strength (CYS) (0.2%), ultimate compressive strength (UCS) and percentage contraction were obtained from the compressive stress-strain curve obtained from compression test. Average of three sample result is considered for the compressive strength of present material.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 X-Ray Diffraction Analysis (XRD)

XRD (X-ray diffraction) analysis of AZ91 can revealed its microstructure, phase composition, and any changes resulting from treatments like annealing or modifications to the casting process. Fig. 03 represented the XRD analysis for the produced magnesium alloy. XRD studies of AZ91 included XRD patterns confirm the presence of the primary α -Mg phase and the secondary $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ intermetallic phase.

Fig. 03 XRD image of produced magnesium alloy AZ91

3.2 SEM analysis

The surface morphology of the AZ91 alloy (T6 heat treated) samples were analysed through SEM. The SEM images are shown in Fig.04. The distribution of primary phase and secondary phase are visible in the SEM image. In addition that this analysis validates the preparation methods well suited for the preparation of magnesium alloy AZ91.

Fig. 04 SEM image of produced Mg alloy

3.3 Discussion on Compression Properties

Fig. 05 Compressive stress strain curve of Mg alloy

Fig. 05 represents the compressive stress strain curve of produced magnesium alloy. The compressive force from 0 N to 32,330 N was applied to the sample gradually in the computerized universal testing machine. This test resulted the ultimate compressive strength of 243 MPa indicates the maximum compressive stress the material can withstand before failure. This value reflects the alloy's ability to resist deformation under a compressive load, which is critical in applications where components are subjected to crushing forces or require high load-bearing capacity. The strain at failure, measured as 10%, indicates the alloy's ductile property ability to undergo plastic deformation before failure. This combination of strength and ductility makes the magnesium alloy suitable for applications requiring energy absorption and resistance to brittle fracture.

It is understood from previous literatures on mechanical properties such as compressive properties are influenced by factors such as alloy composition, microstructure, and manufacturing processes. Alloying elements like aluminum and zinc, often present in magnesium alloys, contribute to solid solution strengthening and the formation of intermetallic phases that enhance strength. Processing techniques such as heat treatment further refine the microstructure, leading to improved mechanical performance. In addition the compressive yield strength measured by using 0.2% offset method and indicated that 120 MPa as compressive yield strength of produced magnesium alloy.

Hence produced magnesium alloy possessed a compressive strength of 243 MPa and 10% ductility exhibits a commendable balance of mechanical properties, making it a adaptable material for load-bearing and

impact-resistant applications. Further optimization of the alloy's properties through advanced manufacturing techniques can unlock its potential for even more demanding engineering challenges. Table 1 represents the obtained compression properties of produced magnesium alloy AZ91.

Table 1. Compressive properties of produced magnesium alloy AZ91

Sample	Condition	Compressive Yield strength (CYS) (0.2 %)	Ultimate Compressive strength (UCS)	Elongation
		MPa	MPa	%
Stir-casted magnesium alloy AZ91	As-cast	120	243	10

3.4 Finite Element Analysis on Compression Properties

Fig. 06 Finite element model for Compression test of Mg alloy

Fig. 06 illustrates the Finite Element model for performing compression test on magnesium alloy through ANSYS software. The compression test model involves simulating the behavior of a material under compressive loading, typically using a Finite Element Analysis (FEA) approach. This study aimed to predict material compressive stress, strain, and potential failure points under compressive loads. The process involves defining the material's properties, applying the compressive load, and analyzing the resulting deformation and stress distribution. Material models, such as those for plastic deformation

behavior, can be used to obtain the material's response more accurately, particularly this can be used where the material exhibits non-linear behavior under compression.

Fig. 07 Compressive deformation behavior of Mg alloy for 5 mm deformation

Fig. 08 Compressive deformation behavior of Mg alloy for 10 mm deformation

Fig. 07 and 08 represents the Finite Element analysis results for compression test on magnesium alloy through ANSYS software. This compression test was conducted in ANSYS for 5 mm and 10 mm deformations revealed the material's progressive response under increasing compressive strain. At 5 mm deformation (Fig. 07), the stress distribution is relatively uniform could be visible in the image, it indicated the elastic behavior with minor localized stress concentrations, suggesting the structure remains within its elastic limit. However, In contrast, at 10 mm deformation (Fig. 08), the results show significantly higher stress intensities and broader zones of plastic deformation are visible in the image, this indicated that the

material begins to yield and accumulate permanent deformation. This transition highlights the onset of material nonlinearity and potential failure regions, providing crucial insights into the structural limits and safety margins under compressive loading. This study particularly applicable for magnesium-based material for compressive load applications in particular for structural and automobile applications.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this present study, AZ91 magnesium alloy was produced through novel stir casting method. The microstructure and compression properties were studied through experimentally. In addition finite element analysis also carried out to analyse the compression behavior. The following results were obtained from this study.

- i) Stir casting process can be one of the novel and economical method for preparing the magnesium based materials.
- ii) XRD study confirmed the presence of α -Mg phase and the secondary $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ intermetallic phases.
- iii) SEM image also studied for morphology analysis for produced Mg alloy.
- iv) The compression test was performed at room temperature and obtained ultimate compressive strength 243 MPa, compressive yield strength of 120 MPa and 10% ductility.
- v) Finite element analysis also carried out for this material and outcome revealed the 10 mm deflection study indicated more stress intensities and broader zone of plastic deformation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to Manufacturing Research Laboratory, Department of Mechanical Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Puducherry, for encouragement and support for these experimental studies.

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